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INCREASING MUTTON PRODUCTION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SHEEP BREEDING IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The article presents information on the creation of a new "Aqchasoy" type of meat-oriented sheep by improving the breeding and productive qualities of existing sheep, effectively using the genetic potential of pedigree sheep characteristic of the world gene pool through targeted breeding work in Uzbek sheep breeding. Also, the possibility of conducting selection work based on the identified positive correlation coefficients in improving breeding traits of F₁ hybrid generations obtained from the Dagestan and meat-wool breeds using breeding and genetic parameters, increasing the volume of meat production and regularly replenishing herds with pedigree sheep through the development of intensive breeding technology for fattening rams has been substantiated. In the research, the creation of new types of highly productive sheep and their improvement, increasing the volume of mutton production through the application of intensive innovative technologies in the industry, serve the implementation of the tasks set for the development of sheep breeding in our republic.

Key words: selection, new type, breed, ram, sheep, lamb, flock, live weight, meat, wool.

Introduction. Sheep breeding is one of the important branches of animal husbandry, providing the population with valuable products such as meat, wool, and fat. Increasing meat production through the improvement of breeding and productive traits of sheep and the effective use of their genetic potential is of great importance for the development of the industry. In Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to improving local sheep breeds and creating new highly productive types adapted to local conditions. In this regard, studying the relationships between the main selection traits and using breeding and genetic parameters in selection work is an important scientific and practical task. In Uzbekistan, special attention is also given to the development of sheep breeding through the improvement of existing local breeds and the creation of new productive types using advanced breeding and genetic approaches. The effective use of the genetic potential of fat-tailed sheep breeds and their hybrids contributes to increasing meat production and improving the productivity indicators of flocks. Therefore, the development of new productive sheep types and the improvement of selection work based on breeding and genetic parameters are essential for increasing the volume of mutton production and strengthening the breeding base of the sheep industry.

Relevance of the topic. In the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. DP-60 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" the

tasks of strengthening scientific research aimed at “increasing the income of dekhkans and farmers by at least 2 times through the intensive development of agriculture on a scientific basis, bringing the annual growth of agriculture to at least 5 percent, as well as expanding the fodder base of animal husbandry and increasing the volume of production by 1.5-2 times” improving breeding and selection work, improving the breeding, productive and reproductive characteristics of breeds, creating their productive lines, families, types and breeds are defined.

In the world, sheep breeding is one of the main branches. In Australia, England, New Zealand, Spain, Germany, the Netherlands, France, the USA, Italy, and other countries with developed sheep breeding, as well as in the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States - Russia, Belarus, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, and Tajikistan, the breeding of fat-tailed sheep is mainly focused on the production of high-quality young mutton in demand on the international market, as well as on the production of carpets, knitwear, and various types of fabrics from sheep wool that meet the requirements for processing in the light industry. In this regard, the systematic use of the genetic potential of fat-tailed sheep breeds of the meat and fat direction and, on this basis, the creation of promising populations with high meat productivity and consolidated heredity, along with valuable biological characteristics, is of great importance and relevance for the rapid increase in the efficiency of this industry [1,3,4,5].

In order to meet the population's demand for meat and meat products in sheep breeding, a number of important measures are being implemented in the republic to improve the breeding and productivity characteristics of fat-tailed sheep of the existing meat and fat production direction by biotechnological methods, and to introduce intensive innovative technologies into production by improving optimal pasture feeding conditions. Also, in our republic, a number of scientific research works have been carried out on the preservation, reproduction of the gene pool of sheep with fine and semi-fine wool and improvement of their productive characteristics, as well as the creation of highly productive flocks, improvement of economically useful traits using the hereditary potential of the breed, and the results obtained have been implemented in practice [2,6,7].

The aim of the research. Creation of a new "Aqchasoy" type of meat-oriented sheep by improving the breeding and productive qualities of Uzbek coarse-wooled fat-tailed sheep, development of a technology for intensive fattening of rams, conducting selection work based on the identified positive correlation coefficients using selection and genetic parameters, improving the selection traits of F₁ hybrid generations of the Dagestan and meat-wool breeds.

Place and object of research. Research work was carried out in breeding farms specializing in sheep breeding in Tashkent and Fergana regions. When conducting scientific research, zootechnical: live weight, fertility (ВИЖ methodology, 1978); biological: growth, development, exterior, body structure indices, clinical and hematological indicators were determined using generally accepted methods, wool productivity - according to the method of Калинин В.В. “Методика изучения качества шерсти” (ВИЖ 1970), selection and genetic indicators - according to the method of Шиллер Р., Вахал Я., Винш Я. “Математика в животноводстве” (1970), statistical: arithmetic mean and its error, the degree of reliability of the intergroup difference - according to the method of Меркурева Е.К. “Биометрия в селекции и генетике сельскохозяйственных животных” (1970).

Research results. In the creation of the new type, long-term work was carried out on the selection and mating of hybrids born from crossing purebred Hissar breed rams with local Jaidari breed ewes. In this case, systems of highly productive breeding rams of the Charkinsay and Tokkuzbulak varieties, not related to each other, were created, and work was carried out on “within

oneself” breeding of highly productive ewes of this breed with rams of optimal productivity and breed. For many years, in-depth selection work was carried out on high-yielding hybrids obtained from “within oneself” breeding, and breeding flocks were formed. A new type of meat-oriented fat-tailed sheep “Akchasoy” has been created, which meets the requirements of the optimal productive type, whose productivity, external and reproductive characteristics, as well as viability, remain unchanged for many years and can transmit economically useful traits from generation to generation.

Requirements for the optimal productivity type for live weight of sheep of the Akchasai type have been developed, the superiority of the new type in terms of live weight over the standard requirements of the Jaidari breed is presented in Table 1.

Table 1**Jaidari by live weight of Akchasai type sheep breed superiority over standard requirements**

№	Groups	Akchasai type		Jaidari reed	Difference,%
		average	record-reakings		
1	Pedigree rams	110	120-180	80	37
2	Ewes	65	70-75	55	15
3	1,5 age pedigree rams	70	75-90	60	18
4	1,5 age pedigree female sheeps	50	55-65	40	25
5	5 month age ram lambs	42	50-60	35	20
6	5 month age female lambs	38	45-55	32	19
7	At the birth of ram lambs	6,0	6,5-7,0	5,5	10
8	At the birth of female lambs	5,5	6,0-6,5	5,0	10
	Average				20

As can be seen from the table data, the average live weight of pedigree rams of the new "Akchasoy" type is 110 kg, ewes - 65 kg, 1,5 age pedigree rams - 70 kg, 1,5 age pedigree female sheeps for replenishing the flock - 50 kg, 5 month age ram lambs after weaning - 45 kg, females - 40 kg, ram lambs at birth – 6,0 kg, females – 5,5 kg, respectively, compared to peers of the pure Jaidari breed - 30 kg or 37%; 10 kg or 15%; 10 kg or 18%; 10 kg or 25%; 7,0 kg or 20%; 6,0 kg or 19%; 0,5 kg or 10%; 0,5 kg or 10% higher.

These results, regardless of sex and age, were characterized by a live weight of 20% higher than the standard requirements of the Jaidari breed, which indicates an increase in the volume of sheep production and serves to provide the population with meat products.

In the research, it is important to conduct research on increasing the meat productivity of rams through the technology of intensive growth ram (Table 2).

Table 2**Meat-fat productivity of ram lambs, (n=3)**

Groups	Pre-slaughter live weight, kg	Carcass weight, kg	Relative to live weight, %	Internal fat, kg	Relative to live weight, %	Tail fat, kg	Relative to live weight, %	Slaughtering	
	M±m	M±m		M±m		M±m		weight, kg	Dress-ing percentage, %
at 6 months of age									
Control	36,9±0,27	15,2±0,15	40,9	0,5±0,06	1,5	1,7±0,1	4,7	17,4±0,1	46,6
Experimental	40,2±0,25***	17,2±0,12***	41,3	0,5±0,06	1,3	2,1±0,1**	5,0	19,8±0,1***	47,5
at 12 months of age									
Control	46,2±0,21	19,9±0,1	43,0	1,4±0,06	3,0	2,7±0,1	6,0	24,0±0,21	51,9

Experimental	57,4±0,23 ^{***}	25,0±0,15 ^{***}	43,6	1,7±0,1 ^{**}	3,1	4,0±0,1 ^{***}	7,0	30,7±0,15 ^{***}	53,5
at 12 months of age									
Control	72,9±0,21	31,5±0,15	43,3	2,3±0,11	3,2	5,8±0,1	8,0	39,5±0,26	54,2
Experimental	96,3±0,21 ^{***}	43,0±0,1 ^{***}	44,7	3,3±0,15 ^{***}	3,4	7,8±0,15 ^{***}	8,1	54,5±0,27 ^{***}	56,6

Reminder: ^{}P<0,01; ^{***}P<0,001**

The pre-slaughter weight of 6 month age ram lambs of the Jaidari breed in the control group was 36,9 kg, the pre-slaughter weight of the experimental group was 40,2 km, and the experimental group surpassed the control group by 3,3 kg (P<0,001).

The difference in the weight of the carcass was 2,0 kg (P<0,001). At 12 months of age, the highest pre-slaughter live weight indicators were observed in the experimental group of rams and amounted to 57,4 kg. According to this indicator, it was found that the rams of the control group were 11,2 kg (P<0,001) behind, and the difference in carcass weight was 5,1 kg (P<0,001).

When slaughtering rams at the age of 18 months, the highest pre-slaughter live weight indicators were observed in rams of the experimental group and amounted to 96,3 kg. According to this indicator, it was found that the rams of the control group were 23,4 kg (P<0,001) behind, and the difference in carcass weight was 11,5 kg (P<0,001).

Most of the economically useful traits of sheep are connected to one degree or another. Positive correlation does not always give good results; some traits contradict each other, for example, high meat productivity and easy fertilization of sheep, which somewhat complicates breeding work.

In scientific research, we studied the correlation coefficients between the main selection traits of 12-month-old sheep, the results of which are presented in Table 3.

Table 3

correlation coefficients of lambs between the main selection traits (r-15)

№	Indicators	I		II	
		F ₁ generation		Male	Female
		Male	Female	Male	Female
1	Live weight with withers height	0,190	0,149	0,102	0,128
2	Live weight with oblique body length	-0,318	-0,218	-0,004	-0,180
3	Live weight with chest girth	0,551	0,093	0,304	0,090
4	Withers height with oblique body length	0,922	0,600	0,578	0,512
5	Withers height with chest girth	0,487	0,100	0,003	0,080
6	Chest width with chest depth	0,504	0,163	-0,155	-0,013
7	Chest girth with oblique body length	0,207	0,070	0,022	0,231
8	Cannon bone girth with withers height	-0,279	-0,083	-0,094	-0,445
9	Rump height with withers height	0,997	0,997	0,986	0,712
10	Live weight with absolute growth	0,981	0,976	0,986	0,955
11	Live weight with average daily gain	0,981	0,985	0,975	0,983
12	Absolute growth with average daily gain	0,999	0,994	0,983	0,990

According to Table 3, regardless of sex, a low positive correlation (+0,022 - +0,231) was observed in lambs of groups I and II between live weight and withers height, chest girth, as well as between chest girth and oblique body length. A low negative correlation (-0,004 - -0,445) was detected between live weight and oblique body length, and between cannon bone girth and withers height.

Based on the correlation indicators between the main selection traits, a high positive correlation (+0,600 - +0,999) was identified in Group I between withers height and oblique body

length. In addition, regardless of sex, lambs in Groups I and II showed a strong positive relationship between live weight and absolute growth, live weight and average daily gain, as well as between absolute growth and average daily gain.

Thus, in order to replenish flocks with breeding sheep, conducting selection based on the high positive correlation coefficients identified between the main selection traits of Dagestan and meat–wool F₁ hybrid lambs will increase the efficiency of selection. This approach is also of significant importance in the formation and development of “pedigree flocks”.

Conclusion. Regardless of sex and age, sheep of the “Akchasai” type were characterized by live weight indicators that were 20% higher than the standard requirements of the Jaidari breed, which indicates an increased potential for livestock production in sheep farming. Through the development of an intensive fattening technology for rams, the highest pre-slaughter live weight at 18 months of age was observed in the rams of the experimental group, reaching 96,3 kg. According to this indicator, they exceeded the rams of the control group by 23,4 kg, while the carcass weight was 11,5 kg higher. According to the correlation coefficients between the main selection traits of meat–wool sheep, the F₁ hybrid offspring with Dagestan and meat–wool genotypes demonstrated the most favorable indicators. In particular, a high positive correlation (+0,981 - +0,999) was observed between withers height and oblique body length in lambs, as well as between live weight and absolute growth, live weight and average daily gain, and between absolute growth and average daily gain. Through the purposeful implementation of breeding and selection work, effective use of the genetic potential of breeding sheep belonging to the world gene pool, and the application of intensive innovative technologies in the sector, it is possible to develop and improve new highly productive sheep types and increase the volume of sheep production. This will have significant practical importance for the development of sheep breeding in the Republic.

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